

Summary of calculations of radial neutron flux distributions in a KBS-3 type geological repository for spent nuclear fuel

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1 Summarised model description

The monte carlo radiation transport toolkit Geant4, version 10.6.2 [1], has been used to calculate the radial distribution of neutron flux per emitted neutron from rods of spent nuclear fuel in a KBS-3 type geological repository. Using the model of the KBS-3 repository with geometry and materials as detailed in [2], neutrons with one energy were emitted from one fuel rod in one assembly in the copper canister. The Geant4 physics list entitled QGSP_BERT_HP was used to model the transport of neutrons in the system.

The energy of emitted neutrons and the emission rod were varied in order to calculate the neutron flux in a cylindrical mesh (with varying radii) centered on the center axis of the canister, as a response function of emitting rod and neutron energy. The spatial distribution of emitted neutrons was homogeneous over the fuel rod, i.e. with no internal or radial variation. The water ratio of the Bentonite clay buffer was varied with seven discrete values between 0 and 0.28, according to what might be expected in the repository over a time period up to hundreds of thousands of years. Besides the variation of water content in the clay, nominal geometry and material specifications according to [2] were used with the canister packed full with twelve spent nuclear fuel assemblies of the boiling water reactor (BWR) SVEA-96S type.

This report describes the format of the data files comprising the results of the calculations.

2 Data structure

Results from the calculations were saved in a structured query language (SQL) database. The structured relationship between the data tables are illustrated by the SQL schema definitions in section 2.1. When all calculations were finished, the tables in the database were exported to comma separated values' text files (CSV files). All CSV files are stored in a publicly available Zenodo archive, see reference [3].

The neutron flux per emitted particle were saved in table MeshSum, which contains the sum of the calculated neutron fluxes (for a specific emission source configuration) as well the number of emitted neutron used to generate that summed value. The flux per emitted particle can be calculated as the ratio between the sum value and number of emitted particles.

Numbering of fuel rods and insert holes in the canister for spent fuel assemblies, which are specified in table `GeometrySourceConfiguration`, follow the same numbering as used for the study in reference [2].

In order to enable a study of convergence, the MeshSum table was saved at many occasions during the calculations, providing snapshots of the current value sum and number of emitted particles. An extra CSV file is available in the data archive [3] which contain these snapshots, named `meshsum_cumulative.csv`.

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2.1 SQL schema

Listing 1: The SQL schema defining the relations between the data tables. This schema definition is available in the file named `schema.sql` in reference [3].

```
CREATE TABLE SourceParticle (
    Id INTEGER PRIMARY KEY
    ,Name VARCHAR(128) NOT NULL UNIQUE
);
CREATE TABLE Bentonite (
    Id INTEGER PRIMARY KEY
    ,DryDensity_kg_per_m3 REAL NOT NULL
    CHECK( DryDensity_kg_per_m3 >= 1000.0 AND DryDensity_kg_per_m3 <= 1800.0 )
    ,WaterRatio REAL NOT NULL
    CHECK( WaterRatio >= 0.0 AND WaterRatio <= 1.0 )
    ,CONSTRAINT Bentonite_uq
    UNIQUE( DryDensity_kg_per_m3 , WaterRatio )
);
CREATE TABLE GeometrySourceConfiguration (
    Id INTEGER PRIMARY KEY
    ,FuelId INTEGER NOT NULL
    ,SourcePinNumber INTEGER NOT NULL
    ,SourceParticleId INTEGER NOT NULL
    ,SourceParticleEnergy_eV REAL NOT NULL
    ,SourceInsertHoleColumnIndex INTEGER NOT NULL
    ,SourceInsertHoleRowIndex INTEGER NOT NULL
    ,BentoniteId INTEGER NOT NULL
    ,CONSTRAINT GeometrySourceConfiguration_fk2
    FOREIGN KEY(SourceParticleId)
    REFERENCES SourceParticle(Id)
    ON DELETE RESTRICT ON UPDATE RESTRICT
    ,CONSTRAINT GeometrySourceConfiguration_fk3
    FOREIGN KEY(BentoniteId)
    REFERENCES Bentonite(Id)
    ON DELETE RESTRICT ON UPDATE RESTRICT
    ,CONSTRAINT GeometrySourceConfiguration_uq
    UNIQUE(
        FuelId ,
        SourcePinNumber ,
        SourceParticleId ,
        SourceParticleEnergy_eV ,
        SourceInsertHoleColumnIndex ,
        SourceInsertHoleRowIndex ,
        BentoniteId)
);
CREATE TABLE Index3D(
    Id INTEGER PRIMARY KEY
    ,i INTEGER NOT NULL
    ,j INTEGER NOT NULL
    ,k INTEGER NOT NULL
    ,CONSTRAINT Index3D_uk UNIQUE(i ,j ,k)
);
CREATE TABLE Scorer (
    Id INTEGER PRIMARY KEY
    ,Name TEXT NOT NULL UNIQUE
    ,Unit TEXT NOT NULL
```

```

,UnitValue REAL NOT NULL
,NumOfSegments_i INTEGER NOT NULL
,NumOfSegments_j INTEGER NOT NULL
,NumOfSegments_k INTEGER NOT NULL
,DivisionAxisName_i TEXT NOT NULL
,DivisionAxisName_j TEXT NOT NULL
,DivisionAxisName_k TEXT NOT NULL
);
CREATE TABLE Mesh (
  Id INTEGER PRIMARY KEY
,Name TEXT NOT NULL UNIQUE
);
CREATE TABLE ConfigMeshScorer (
  Id INTEGER PRIMARY KEY
,GeometrySourceConfigurationId INTEGER NOT NULL
,MeshId INTEGER NOT NULL
,ScorerId INTEGER NOT NULL
,CONSTRAINT ConfigMeshScorer_uk
  UNIQUE(GeometrySourceConfigurationId ,MeshId ,ScorerId)
,CONSTRAINT ConfigMeshScorer_GeometrySourceConfigurationId_fk
  FOREIGN KEY(GeometrySourceConfigurationId)
  REFERENCES GeometrySourceConfiguration (Id)
  ON DELETE RESTRICT ON UPDATE RESTRICT
,CONSTRAINT ConfigMeshScorer_MeshId_fk
  FOREIGN KEY(MeshId)
  REFERENCES Mesh (Id)
  ON DELETE RESTRICT ON UPDATE RESTRICT
,CONSTRAINT ConfigMeshScorer_ScorerId_fk
  FOREIGN KEY(ScorerId)
  REFERENCES Scorer (Id)
  ON DELETE RESTRICT ON UPDATE RESTRICT
);
CREATE TABLE MeshSum (
  ConfigMeshScorerId INTEGER NOT NULL
,Index3DId INTEGER NOT NULL
,Value REAL NOT NULL
,NumberOfEvents INTEGER NOT NULL
,CONSTRAINT MeshSum_PK PRIMARY KEY( ConfigMeshScorerId ,Index3DId)
,CONSTRAINT MeshSum_ConfigMeshScorer_fk
  FOREIGN KEY(ConfigMeshScorerId)
  REFERENCES ConfigMeshScorer (Id)
  ON DELETE RESTRICT ON UPDATE RESTRICT
,CONSTRAINT MeshSum_Index3DId_fk2
  FOREIGN KEY(Index3DId)
  REFERENCES Index3D (Id)
  ON DELETE RESTRICT ON UPDATE RESTRICT
);

```

3 Acknowledgements

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References

- [1] S. Agostinelli et al. “Geant4—a simulation toolkit”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 506.3 (2003), pp. 250–303. ISSN: 0168-9002. DOI: [10.1016/S0168-9002\(03\)01368-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-9002(03)01368-8).
- [2] P. Jansson et al. “A new methodology for thermal analysis of geological disposal of spent nuclear fuel using integrated simulations of gamma heating and finite element modeling”. In: *Annals of Nuclear Energy* 172 (2022), p. 109082. ISSN: 0306-4549. DOI: [10.1016/j.anucene.2022.109082](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2022.109082).
- [3] P. Jansson. *Data from calculated radial neutron flux distributions in a KBS-3 type geological repository*. June 2022. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.6584076](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6584076).